

Improve your findability

Ensuring potential users can easily find your resource is key to expanding your user base. Here are some tips to begin with:

By Search Engines

To enhance your Search Engine Optimisation (SEO), start by analyzing the **keywords** that lead visitors to your website. To achieve this, go to "Acquisition > Search Engines & Keywords" in [SIB Matomo](#). For instance, if your resource is mostly discovered by its name rather than through search queries related to scientific topics, it indicates that:

- Your resource has a **strong brand recognition**.
- Most of your users are existing ones, suggesting an opportunity to **attract new users**. Consult the factsheet dedicated to «**Attracting attention to your resource**» to gain visibility towards potential users.

Below you will find a set of **basic rules for SEO**. They are not intended to be exhaustive and apply first to Google. Conduct a self-assessment and follow these SEO recommendations to **improve your search engine visibility**.

→ Check your code

- Ensure **markup validity** with the [W3C validator](#) and **code brevity** (15% of tags, max)
- Serve your site in **HTTPS**
- Have a **short domain name**
- Embed valid **schema.org metadata** in the **JSON-LD format** in the head element (check with [Schema validator](#)).
- Use **semantic HTML elements** such as `<h1>` or `<table>` instead of `` or `<div>` for a clearer meaning for browsers and developers. Especially when using header tags, use them in order `h1`, `h2`, `h3`, ... Do not skip tags.
- Add **alt properties** to image and link tags
- Provide a **sitemap**.
- Regularly check that **links are not broken** (using SEO tool suites or XENU Link Sleuth, for example)

→ Check your design

- Implement **responsive design**
- Add the **Resource logo at the top left** of each page as a link to the homepage
- Add a **search field**
- Use a **personalized 404 error** page with key links like home, about, etc.
- Add **breadcrumbs** on top of pages to clarify navigation for both search engines and users

→ Check performance/speed

- The time Google spends crawling your website is limited. If loading/rendering your pages takes too much time, the indexing might be impaired.
- Check your website performance with [SIB Matomo](#), [GTmetrix](#), and/or [PageSpeed Insights](#).
 - Use **minified** JS and CSS files
 - No slideshow, Google map, etc. or **other long to load/render elements** on the homepage
 - Use [Server-Side Rendering \(SSR\)](#) over Single-Page Applications (SPAs) built with React

→ Define keywords

Help Google understand page content by including a definition of search query terms in your pages.

To select keywords, you can use [Google Trends](#), the [AdWord keyword planner](#), [Ubersuggest](#), or [ChatGPT](#) - there are plenty of prompt examples online. Then use these keywords or terms with equivalent meaning:

- in the **URL** (domain name + sub-domains),
- in the **page title**,
- in the **top menu**,
- in the **<h1> tag** and in the **<h2> tags** (in this order),
- in the **text**.

In Registries

→ All resources

Should be listed in (provided they meet the criteria):

- [Expasy.org](#), the Swiss Bioinformatics Resource Portal
- [ELIXIR's bio.tools](#) and their training materials in [TeSS](#) and [SIB's Glittr.org](#)
- [SciCrunch](#) (includes ontologies)

→ Databases

Should have an entry in:

- [Wikipedia](#) as well as in existing gene or protein pages with information from your resources and/or with links to corresponding entry in resources. Seek advice with the **Communications team** as there are specific rules to get published on Wikipedia (without having a "conflict of interest" banner)
- [NAR Database Summary Paper Alphabetic List](#) (requires a publication in the NAR Database Issue)
- [NAR db status](#) (requires a publication in the NAR Database Issue)
- [Bioregistry.io](#) (includes ontologies)
- [FAIRsharing](#) (includes ontologies) which is included in the Japanese Integbio Database Catalog
- [Database Commons](#), a catalog of worldwide biological databases in China
- [re3data](#), the registry of research data repositories
- [YummyData](#) and [Linked Open Data Cloud](#) (for SPARQL endpoints)

→ Ontologies

Should be included in:

- The National Center for Biomedical Ontology [BioPortal](#), or its derivatives such as [Agroportal](#) for agriculture and [Ecoportal](#) for ecology and related domains.
- The [EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service](#)
- [Ontobee](#), the default linked data server for most [OBO Foundry](#) library ontologies

→ Software tools

Should consider:

- Making their code public on [GitHub](#)
- Packaging their code and environment using [Conda](#) (Conda and standard Python packages)
- Publishing Python packages in [PyPi](#)
- Sharing your open-source software in [Bioconductor](#)
- Distributing container images in [Docker hub](#) and/or [Quay Container Registry](#)
- Listing their packages (e.g conda), containers (e.g docker, singularity) and workflows in [BioContainers](#)

→ Datasets

Should be deposited in [Zenodo](#) to obtain a DOI and record their metadata.

Pay attention to how you gain new users

Identifying the main channels that drive new visitors to your website — such as search engines, direct access, or referrals — can help you boost your traffic. To evaluate this, check the "Acquisition > Overview" section in [SIB Matomo](#).

Your contacts:

[Communications team](#)
[Biodata Resources team](#)

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